

THE IMPACT OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE: CASE STUDY OF THE BANKING SECTOR IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: This paper studies the impact of corporate social responsibility on organizational performance using Nigeria's banking sector as a case study. The aim is to investigate (i) To discover the effect of human rights responsibility on the performance of the Nigerian banking sector, (ii) To discover the effect of human rights responsibility on the performance of the Nigerian banking sector, (iii) To measure the effect of economic responsibility on the performance of the banking sector in Nigeria, and (iv) To investigate the impact of philanthropic responsibility on the banking sector. The results of the regression analysis using the data for 398 respondents drawn from employees of 22 banks in Nigeria, show that corporate social responsibility represented by its variables; Environmental responsibility, human rights responsibility, philanthropic responsibility and Economic responsibility, positively impacts on organizational performance of Nigerian Banks.

Keywords: corporate social responsibility, banking sector, Economic responsibility, Nigerian Banks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Every firm focuses on creating enduring and beneficial relationships with customers and society at large in today's fiercely competitive business environment in order to ensure long-term financial sustainability (Boafo & Kokuma, 2016). The idea of corporate social responsibility has been recognised and accepted by certain corporations as a means of improving performance. A strong impetus toward corporate social responsibility (CSR) has resulted from corporations' intense concern with their credibility in regard to their social and environmental commitments as a result of globalisation (Perrini & Tencati, 2006). To demonstrate and improve their environmental and social resilience as well as their duty, businesses, nevertheless, consistently engage in CSR efforts (Farache & Perks, 2010). The study of corporate responsibility is a significant area in business ethics. Theories of corporate social responsibility now in existence assume that businesses rely on society for continuity, expansion, and sustainability. Businesses are most likely to have a good impact on society when they treat society fairly (Husillos, González, & Gil, 2011). An organization's attempts to maximize its positive customer impact while minimizing its negative social impact are referred to as corporate social responsibility (CSR) (Brinkmann & Peattie, 2008). The term "corporate social responsibility" (CSR) refers to how firms conduct their business in a way that is moral, socially responsible, and useful to the community (Ismail, 2009). CSR refers to a business' duty to safeguard and promote welfare benefits while giving stakeholders long-term rewards (Lin et al., 2009). CSR has been a key component of many companies' corporate strategies for reducing their negative social and environmental effects (Beret, 2011). The performance of a corporation can be impacted in a number of ways by corporate social

responsibility. It helps to strengthen the company's financial situation so that it can expand swiftly and generate the greatest amount of income in the market. A company will surely be able to outperform its rivals if it upholds CSR and works to satisfy its stakeholders. Over the past few decades, there has been a striking increase in the difficulties and activities related to corporate social responsibility." A protracted debate has broken out among shareholders, stakeholders, and community organisations regarding who will benefit and who will suffer the cost of implementing CSR activities as a result of growing awareness of the necessity and need of CSR among them" (Tsoutsoura, 2004).

Businesses are held accountable not only to investors but also to groups including shareholders, consumers, employees, and the community as the economy expands and business strategies advance. In essence, it is a partnership between businesses and nonprofits committed to promoting societal and local development. The evolving view of corporate responsibility places more emphasis on the welfare of stakeholders (workers, clients, suppliers, management, and society) than it does on the interests of shareholders through profit maximisation.

Social effect and philanthropy are a company's heart and soul (Levy, 1999). Combining a social purpose with a business goal and outlining the corporate social responsibility principles. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) behavior refers to the social activities that corporations engage in. Recently, organizations and society have given more attention to these activities (Margolis & Walsh, 2001). (Carroll, 1979). Businesses who recognized the value of CSR, its influence on society, and its long-term advantages voluntarily included CSR into their main business operations. The following are some advantages of including CSR in a company's strategies: a source of leverage for the business, a vital and useful resource for a competitive edge, a confident corporate strategy, and a sizeable financial and efficient marketing tool to establish and maintain a competitive edge (Porter & Kramer, 2006). (Maignan & Ferrell, 2001).

Over the years, researchers from all over the world have closely studied corporate social responsibility and how it affects business performance (Jin & Drozdenko, 2010; Petrenko, Aime, Ridge, & Hill, 2016). Contradictory findings have been found in a number of studies that looked at the direct connection between corporate social responsibility and business effectiveness (Margolis & Walsh, 2003; Mishra & Suar, 2010; Vogel, 2005). Despite the fact that some studies (Abu-Bakar & Ameer, 2011, Van-Beurden & Gössling, 2008, Malcolm, Khadijah, & Ahmad Marzuki, 2007) discovered a positive correlation between corporate responsibility and performance, other studies (Abu-Bakar & Ameer, 2011, Van-Beurden & Gössling, 2008, etc.) discovered a negative correlation.

However, despite the fact that society is largely aware of the negative impacts of corporate operations, these businesses are truly worried about how the performance of all stakeholders is impacted by ethics and social responsibility (Hopkins, 2003). Despite the apparent financial repercussions of fusing stockholder interests with moral, social, and environmental concerns of other stakeholders, many of today's top business CEOs have made large investments in CSR projects (McPeak & Tooley, 2008). These business leaders claim that CSR programs have many advantages over their expenses, including improved staff morale, customer loyalty, and other types of social capital (Parket & Eibert, 1975; Soloman & Hansen, 1985; Moskowitz, 1972). However, some academics still hold that businesses who take part in socially responsible projects will likely experience commercial disadvantages when compared to businesses that don't. This is because it is thought that these expenses don't offer any cash potential (Aupperle, et al., 1985; Vance, 1975; Ullmann, 1985).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Chebet and Muturi (2017) define organizational performance as the evaluation of how well a company performs in relation to its goals and objectives. The three primary outcomes evaluated within organizations are financial success, market performance, and shareholder value performance (in some cases, production capacity performance may be analyzed).

Organizational performance, according to Ali (2014); Malik, Ali, and Ishfaq (2015), refers to the measurements used to assess how well a firm performs. The attainment of corporate objectives through the use of internal and external resources for the accomplishment of organizational goals through high productivity and efficiency was characterized as a firm's performance. Organizational performance refers to a leader's capacity to bring all elements of a company together so that they cooperate to pursue and accomplish set organizational goals in order to increase performance and safeguard competitive advantage. Employee capacity development, knowledge, and creativity, skill and ability enhancement through specialized trainings, and behavior management as integrated into company culture are sources of strengthening competitive advantage.

The Institutional and Organizational Assessment (IOA) Model is one of the most complete frameworks for organizational performance assessment (OPA). The International Development Resource Centre and Universalis explain how it operates (IDRC). According to this paradigm, an organization's performance can be thought of as a multifaceted concept that balances its efficiency, effectiveness, relevance, and financial viability. The framework states that the motivation, capability, and external environment of the organisation should all be taken into consideration when assessing organisational performance. Consequently, organisational performance should be evaluated using a range of metrics, depending on the type of business, including effectiveness, efficiency, customer satisfaction, and financial leverage (IDRC, 2002).

Measuring organisational performance can be difficult, especially for businesses with many goals such as employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction, productivity, profitability, flexibility to a continuously changing environment, and social responsibility. Although scholars have argued for a more comprehensive performance construct that takes non-financial elements like effectiveness, efficiency, quality, and brand perception into account, organizational performance has traditionally been measured in terms of financial indicators. (Waiganjo, Mukulu & Kahiri, 2012).

In comparing corporate social responsibility with firm performance, some scholars have suggested that CSR can boost a company's long-term competitiveness, implying a favourable correlation between a company's involvement in CSR and its ability to succeed financially (Qu, 2017). The aspect of CSR that is least understood is the connection between it and financial performance (Al-ma'ani, Al-Qudah, & Husam Shrouf, 2019). Although studies have found a weakly positive correlation, this association has not been completely demonstrated, and it is unclear how CSR might boost businesses' financial success (Sagebien & Lindsay, 2018). The majority of scholars agree that firms with strong corporate reputations benefit strategically from having them. Businesses with significant assets and a competitive advantage might anticipate making more money. People with hard-to-replicate assets may also experience longer-term higher financial performance (Qu, 2017).

A company's reputation is founded on a number of characteristics that are associated with it and deduced from its past actions and capacity to produce consistently better financial performance. Relevant is also stakeholder belief in the company's success. A company can improve its brand reputation by being financially stable, providing high-quality products and services, having excellent management, and being competitive in the market. Turban and Greening (1997) asserted that CSR programs have a positive link with corporate reputation, which helps attract talented future employees, based on the social identity theory. Industry-specific social responsibility varies, though, with some companies putting a strong emphasis on environmental stewardship while others aim to live up to stakeholder expectations in order to have a positive reputational impact. A company's social practices are also more likely to resonate with stakeholders who support socially conscious business operations. More intriguingly, these stakeholders will devise a plan and sustain these practices in the way that is most profitable for the company so they may benefit from its reputation. In support of this, Saeidi et al. (2015), Zhu et al. (2014), and Roberts and Dowling (2002) discovered a favorable link when examining the relationship between CSR and firm performance using corporate reputation as a mediator. Clearly, there is a significant variation in how much CSR aids companies in enhancing their reputation. According to some experts, well-known companies prioritize CSR more than other companies do (Kim, 2011). Furthermore, according to some studies, companies with a poor reputation are more likely to engage in CSR activities because they think that doing so will improve stakeholders' impressions of the company's reputation (Yoon, Canli, & Schwarz, 2006). It has been noted that the capacity to mould the reputation attained through CSR might influence socially responsible behaviour and stakeholders' favourable perceptions. Stakeholder theory, which contends that stakeholders link a company's reputation with socially responsible behaviour, addresses this. A corporation performs better when its corporate social responsibility initiatives are in line with its reputation.

In defining Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Brinkmann & Peattie, 2008, see it as a company's commitment to maximise its positive effect on stakeholders while minimising its adverse effects on the community. The phrase "corporate social responsibility" refers to a range of organisational approaches used by firms to carry out their various commercial operations in an ethical manner while simultaneously fostering growth in the greater community in which they operate (Ismail, 2009). Additionally, CSR entails a serious duty to protect and enhance the present and long-term sustainability of its allied stakeholders (Lin et al., 2009). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is the practise of businesses or organisations taking part in initiatives that benefit both the company and the society in which they operate (Khanifar, Nazari, Emami, & Soltani, 2018).

Businesses employ corporate social responsibility as a strategy to achieve a competitive edge (Ching, Yin, Pei, Zhi & Pei, 2018). CSR promotes a company's position and perception, which increases competition (Carroll & Shabana, 2018; Chung & Safdar, 2018; Togun & Nasieku,

2018). It requires managing several stakeholder relationships at once, which lowers the possibility of unfavourable legislative, regulatory, or budgetary action and draws in socially conscious customers and investors (Freeman et al., 2018). By strengthening ties with staff, clients, and other stakeholders, stakeholder engagement enhances and supports a business' ability to generate revenue (Harrison & Wicks, 2018). From the outdated perspective of firm performance as a profit-maximizing economic actor to a more ethical perspective that considers business's larger impact on society, the connection between business and society has experienced a great transformation (Safwat, 2017).

2.1 Corporate Social Responsibility and Organizational Performance

It has taken a lot of work to determine how CSR efforts affect organizational performance (Husted & Salazar, 2016; Marom, 2016; Moneva, Bonilla & Ortas 2017; Orlitzky, Schmidt & Rynes, 2003). According to Pava and Krausz's (2015) thorough analysis of empirical data on the relationship between CSR and organizational performance, businesses that are considered to meet social responsibility standards outperformed or fared comparably to other businesses that are not necessarily socially responsible. A recent meta-analysis evaluating the association between CSR and organizational performance supports this beneficial relationship (Orlitzky et al., 2003). The goal of corporate social responsibility is to improve organizational performance. Social responsibility, a significant and ongoing element of corporate behavior, is already present. The brand, revenue, and employee involvement of a firm can all benefit significantly from properly managed CSR projects and programs. CSR can aid in the formation of beneficial collaborations. Strategic social responsibility initiatives and competitive advantage are related, according to Nordberg (2014), and when implemented appropriately, CSR initiatives can result in competitive advantages.

Profit and corporate social responsibility have been linked, according to Joyner and Payne's findings from 2002. According to Berman, Wicks, Kotha, and Jones (1999), some CSR components have a favourable and considerable impact on short-term profitability. Amole, Adebisi, and Awolaja (2012) found a relationship between bank profitability and CSR initiatives. Establishing a loyal client base has become a major marketing goal as well as the cornerstone for creating a sustainable competitive advantage, and it is recognised as a crucial goal for a company's survival and success (Dick & Basu, 1994). Lee, Kim, Lee, and Li (2012) found a positive relationship between economic CSR and customer retention. Nareeman and Hassan (2013) claim that economic CSR has a positive and significant effect on customer retention. In their 2006 study on the effect of CSR on organisational performance, Luo and Bhattacharya found a positive correlation between CSR and customer satisfaction. Total customer satisfaction, according to Yu et al. (2005), positively affects customer retention and loyalty.

Employee retention is higher and inclinations to leave the company are lower when they believe their company is socially responsible (Hansen, Dunford, Boss, Boss & Angermeier, 2011). According to Hagen, Huse, and Nielsen, there is a strong correlation between employees and CSR knowledge (2009). According to Lindgreen, Swaen, and Campbell (2009), staff attractiveness and CSR have a positive relationship. Albinger and Freeman (2000) found a correlation between CSR success and employee attractiveness. CSR initiatives can increase employee loyalty and happiness, according to Edmans (2011).

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employed quantitative primary data gathered from the target audience of the selected Nigerian banks. The research plan for this study will be based on causal effect relationships among the variables. In an effort to explore the impact of corporate social responsibility on organizational performance: a case study of the banking sector in Nigeria, we indeed ascertained the link between organizational performance and corporate social responsibility which is proxied by; Environmental Responsibility, Human Rights Responsibility, Philanthropic Responsibility and Economic Responsibility.

Data gathered from the target audience was gotten using structured questionnaire. The 2- sectioned questionnaire sported questions on respondents' demography as well as questions that highlight the four variables that make up the dependent variable.

$$n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)$$

Where:

n= sample size required N = number of people in the population e = allowable error (%)

$$n = 95,026 / 1 + 95,026(0.05)^2$$

n = 398.3233 approximately 398 samples

The population size for this study stood at 95, 026 (Ninety-Five Thousand and Twenty-Six) people, which sums the total number of employees in the 22 commercial banks in Nigeria (according to Statista Research Department, Sep 15, 2021). Of this population, a sample size of 398 (Three Hundred and Ninety-Eight) bank employees. The sample size selection was done randomly so as to ensure all participants have equal chance of being a part of the sample size. The sample size of 398 bank employees was gotten using the Yamane formula (1967).

The ordinary least square regression was utilised to assess the study hypotheses, as well as the covariance was used to examine the close relationships between the variables. While the demography data was analyzed using frequency and percentages and the descriptive technique.

Model Specification

The study shall use a single functional model for the regression analysis. The model is presented as;

$$OgP = (Eco, Phi, Hum, Env) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$OgP = \theta_0 + \theta_1 Eco + \theta_2 Phi + \theta_3 Hum + \theta_4 Env + \mu \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where

OgP = Organization Performance Eco = Economic Responsibility

Phi = Philanthropic Responsibility Hum = Human Right Responsibility Env = Environmental Responsibility

θ_0 = Constant

$\theta_1 - \theta_4$ = Slope

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin - Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.660a	.871	.829	.73574	.435	75.680	4	393	.000	1.930

a. Predictors: (Constant), ENV, PHI, HUM, ECO

b. Dependent Variable: Ogp

The model summary result from the output of the regression is displayed in the table above. The Rsquare demonstrates how well the independent variables (responsibility for the environment, philanthropy, respect for human rights, and economic responsibility) account for changes (variations) in the dependent variable (Organizational performance). The

explanatory factors satisfactorily account for about 87 percent of the fluctuations in the dependent variable, as shown by the R-square value of .871. This is a good explanatory strength and it implies that the model was carefully and correctly formulated, thus its result can be relied upon for policy formulation. The Durbin Watson value shows whether there is an auto correlation problem in the model. Going by its rule, the value 1.930 is approximately equal to two (2) indicating that there is no autocorrelation problem in the model. This implies that the efficiency property of the model is guaranteed.

In testing the relationship between corporate social responsibility and organizational performance, we employed the use of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). From the results obtained, the F statistics value of 75.680 was significant at 0.000 (5% significance level). This therefore signifies that the explanatory variables (Environmental responsibility, Philanthropic responsibility, Human rights responsibility and Economic responsibility) are significant predictors of the dependent variable (Organisational performance).

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	163.866	4	40.967	75.680	.000 ^b
	Residual	212.736	393	.541		
	Total	376.602	397			

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the Relationship Between Corporate Social Responsibility and Organisational performance.

Furthermore, the regression results of the relationship Between Corporate Social Responsibility and Organisational performance, show that Environmental responsibility was a significant predictor of organisational performance at a 5 percent significance level, according to the aforementioned regression finding. Additionally, at a 5% level of significance, philanthropic duty was a strong predictor of organisational performance. Furthermore, even at a 5% significance level, human rights responsibility was a significant predictor of organisational performance. At a 5% level of significance, economic accountability was a significant predictor of organisational performance.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.244	.180		1.356	.176	-.110	.598
	ECO	.296	.061	.247	4.846	.000	.176	.416
	PHI	.210	.051	.204	4.158	.000	.111	.309
	HUM	.291	.058	.248	5.018	.000	.177	.405
	ENV	.137	.058	.113	2.372	.018	.023	.250

Regression Result of the Relationship Between Corporate Social Responsibility and Organisational performance.

In testing the hypothesis, the regression results posit that the null hypothesis one (Ho1: Environmental responsibility has a negative impact on organizational performance of the banking sector in Nigeria) stands rejected and the alternative is accepted. The results of the table above show that the beta value for environmental responsibility is .113 and the p-value (computed level of significance) is 0.018, which equals 0.05. (Alpha level of significance). This proved that being environmentally conscious has a favourable (direct) and substantial effect on organisational performance. As a result, we

draw a conclusion that rejects the study's null hypothesis and accepts the alternative hypothesis, according to which environmental responsibility improves organisational performance in Nigeria's banking sector. This simply means environmental responsibility has a favourable effect on the organisational performance of the Nigerian banking industry. This conclusion is consistent with a study on the impact of CSR on business performance by Garay and Font (2011). Their research showed that CSR has an impact on both customer perceptions and business performance. In a similar line, Skare and Golja (2012), who looked at the connection between corporate social responsibility and financial performance, agreed with the findings. They discovered that businesses that practice corporate responsibility do financially better on average than businesses that don't. Filho, Wanderley, Gomez, and Farache (2010) examined the connection between CSR and a firm's competitive advantage and discovered a strong link between social responsibility, corporate strategy, and competitive advantage. In the new normal of today, where competition moves at the unpredictability of light, an organization's long-term growth, visibility, sustainability, and survival depend on how socially responsible it is to its stakeholders.

Hypothesis two states;

Ho2: Human rights responsibility has a negative effect on the organizational performance of the banking sector in Nigeria

And, according to table above, the outcome of the Beta value is .248 and the human rights responsibility p-value is 0.000, which is 0.05. (Alpha level of significance). This demonstrated that a company's commitment to human rights has a favourable (direct) and considerable impact on its performance. Therefore, we draw a conclusion that rejects the study's null hypothesis and accepts the alternative hypothesis, according to which human rights responsibility enhances organisational performance in Nigeria's banking sector. This result is consistent with that of Nze, Okoh, and Ojeogwu (2016) who claimed that banks engaged in human rights responsibility in order to raise their standards and level of acceptance by society. They also claimed that the effects of CSR, such as a better public image, customer loyalty, fewer regulatory issues, and increased revenue, contributed to organisational success. It is suggested that corporate organisations develop policies on human rights and CSR to serve as a guide and focus efforts on using them to achieve organisational success. Human rights responsibility and CSR demand greater attention and more dedication from business organisations. This study supports the findings of Vieira Jr., Grantham, and Sampson (2021), who found a strong correlation between ROA and a firm's ethical performance.

The null hypothesis three was also rejected by the results of the study. Hypothesis three states; Ho3: Philanthropic responsibility has a positive significant impact on the organizational performance of the banking sector. The B value for philanthropic responsibility in the table above is .204, and the p-value (computed level of significance) is 0.000, which is 0.05. (Alpha level of significance). As a result, this showed that charitable contributions has a favourable (direct) and substantial impact on organisational performance. The alternative hypothesis, which asserts that philanthropic responsibility has a beneficial impact on the organisational performance of the banking industry in Nigeria, is thus accepted, and we draw a conclusion by rejecting the null hypothesis for the study. This conclusion is similar to that of (Dane & Yingcai, 2015), who claimed that most business organisations use charitable CSR to increase their public image with the aim of enhancing patronage, community appreciation, improving harmony within the host communities and the organisation, and ultimately maximising profit. Additionally, a study by Okwemba, Chitiavi, Egessa, Douglas, and Musiega (2014) found a substantial positive link between philanthropic CSR and organisational performance. This indicates that any increase in philanthropic responsibility will improve organisational performance.

The regression results also reject the null hypothesis four which states; Economic responsibility has a negative impact on the organizational performance of the banking sector in Nigeria. The result of the Beta value from the aforementioned table is .247, and the p-value (computed degree of significance) of economic responsibility is 0.000, which is 0.05. (Alpha level of significance). This proved that a sound economic policy has a favourable (direct) and substantial effect on organisational performance. The alternative hypothesis, which argues that economic responsibility has a beneficial impact on the organisational performance of the banking industry in Nigeria, is thus accepted, and we draw a conclusion by rejecting the null hypothesis for the study. This result is consistent with that of Osisiomi, Nzewi, and Nwoye (2015) who looked at the connection between CSR and the success of a few Nigerian companies. Their research showed a strong and positive correlation between CSR expenditures and business profitability, leading them to the conclusion that social responsibility is essential to organisational performance. In addition, Odetayo, Adeyemi, and Sajuyigbe (2014) looked at how CSR affected Nigerian banks' profitability. The authors discovered a strong correlation between Nigerian banks' profitability and their CSR spending.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In today's fiercely competitive global market environment, where high-quality product and service production and effective advertising are no longer assurances that customers will patronise a company, corporate social responsibility has developed into a potent business strategy to gain competitive advantage. Since the interaction between business and society is a reciprocal relationship in which each is dependent on the other for its well-being, stakeholders are now calling on organisations to be more involved in ensuring beneficial activities to the society by meeting their societal expectations as they affect the various stakeholders of the organisations. Today, it is crucial to consider how society views commercial entities in light of their participation in initiatives that advance society as a whole. The importance of CSR engagement cannot be ignored any longer. The community always rewards businesses who genuinely care about her well-being and always finds a way to punish businesses that refuse to participate in CSR initiatives (Sen & Bhattacharya, 2001). Participating in CSR activities has been linked to improved profitability, customer satisfaction, improved organisations' image, increased market share, increased performance, and it also contributes to a higher corporate competitive advantage (Klein & Dawar, 20). These factors all lead to increased profitability, customer satisfaction, improved organisations' image, increased market share, increased performance, and it also attracts new customers to organisations.

Despite the importance placed on the human rights issue in the context of social responsibility, the banks studied in this study revealed low concentrations of CSR practises. This is a result of banks often giving corporate social responsibility little thought. Due to the performance of the banks in Nigeria, this demonstrated that the adoption and execution of corporate social responsibility is still in the developmental stage.

As a result, initiatives should focus on enhancing corporate social responsibility practises among Nigerian banks. This can be achieved by giving social responsibility practises distinctiveness in a way that will elaborate on many forms of social responsibility and how they each transmit diverse signals. Additionally, an effort should be made to simply express the benefits that each sort of corporate social responsibility seeks to provide for the general public.

Based on the discussion of findings of the study, the following recommendations are made

- Banks should involve their key stakeholders when developing CSR programmes for their particular region, since any CSR effort that does not benefit the target population will not be seen favourably. According to Miabho (2010) and Baridam (1995), firms should be cautious about controlling their profitability while also being accountable to society and their stakeholder obligations will pay off in the long term.
- Banks should implement more sensible strategies in Nigeria for implementing their CSR policies.
- Banks should view CSR as a marketing tool or strategy for promoting their goods in order to increase sales profit, customer satisfaction, shareholder return maximisation, stakeholder satisfaction, and image promotion in front of future workers.
- That the banks should step up their efforts to incorporate more dynamic CSR initiatives, such as giving research grants to academic institutions, offering infrastructure development, offering entrepreneur training, etc.

Recommendation for further study: A comprehensive analysis of indigenous banks' CSR initiatives. And also Evaluate how corporate social responsibility has affected Nigeria's banking industry as a whole.

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